

SIGNAL SUBSPACE BASED MINIMUM-VARIANCE SPATIAL ARRAY PROCESSING

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ABSTRACT

The relationship between the traditional minimum-variance distortionless response (MVDR) spatial array beamformer and rank reduced, eigenvector, signal subspace spectrum analysis (SSA) is examined. It is shown that high resolution SSA is simply an enhanced version of the MVDR PSE which is possible when the signal and noise can be parametrically defined. When either the signal does not fit a so-called plane wave assumption and/or the noise is not spatially uncorrelated preprocessing techniques are presented which provide not only rank reduction but also reduced sensitivity to the uncorrelated noise assumption. Examples are provided to illustrate the concepts discussed.

1. INTRODUCTION

The minimum-variance distortionless response (MVDR) criterion for maximum spatial array signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) gain is well established as the basis for discrete sensor adaptive array beamforming [1]. In contrast, signal subspace wavenumber spectrum analysis techniques, which have their origin in the early 1970's [2], do not define a beamforming procedure. In this context, the beamforming function, in the passive/active reception sense, requires that a "beamformer" produce a time series output which can be spectrum analyzed, correlated or even, if need be, listened to. With the exception of the coherent (multipath) arrival condition [3] the true beamforming function of "listening" to the output of a beam formed from an eigenvector weighted sensor array is not even usefully defined. Moreover, it is known that the signal subspace methods unfortunately make the rigid assumption of perfectly coherent signal wavefronts in the presence of spatially uncorrelated noise and are indeed very sensitive to this assumption for threshold signals [4]. Finally,

the application of signal subspace methods to arrays with large numbers of sensors is a computationally intense process. This is particularly true if the realization is with respect to the orthogonal noise subspace eigenvectors as in the MUSIC algorithm [5].

In the following, the relationship between the MVDR beamformer and the signal subspace (wavenumber) spectrum analysis (SSA) is examined first. Then a rank reduction technique is presented which is equivalent to preprocessing with subarray beamformers in sensor arrays and coarse-fine FFT processing in spectrum analysis. Next, the issue of partially coherent noise is considered and it is shown how the simple subarray preprocessor not only reduces realization complexity but improves performance as well. Finally, the coherent multiple (path) signal condition is considered. It is suggested that an alternative to the spatial averaging technique [6], at least for the low SNR and high interference-to-noise (INR) environment, is to simply allow the interference to suppress itself on all arrival paths. The low level coherent multipath signal will not be suppressed anyhow and spatial averaging would result in a net loss of SNR by at least 3dB and inferior resolution.

2.0 MVDR TO SIGNAL SUBSPACE SPECTRUM ANALYSIS

A general cross-spectral density matrix (CSDM) at frequency ω for an N-sensor array is

$$\mathbf{R} = \sigma_s^2 \mathbf{D} \mathbf{E} \mathbf{E}^H + \sigma_c^2 \mathbf{Q} + \sigma_n^2 \mathbf{I} \quad (1a)$$

$$= \mathbf{M} \mathbf{\Lambda} \mathbf{M}^H + \sigma_n^2 \mathbf{I} \quad (1b)$$

where "H" indicates complex conjugate transposition, $\mathbf{D}$ is an NxK signal direction vector matrix for K signals, $\mathbf{E}$ is a KxK signal (complex) envelope coherence matrix, $\mathbf{Q}$ is an NxN partially coherent noise CSDM and $\mathbf{I}$ is an NxN identity matrix. The quantities

σ_s^2 , σ_c^2 and σ_n^2 are the sensor output variances for the signal, coherent noise and uncorrelated noise respectively. In Eq. (1b), the $N \times P$ matrix $\underline{M}$ is the signal plus coherent noise modal matrix with the columns of $\underline{M}$ as the eigenvectors of $\underline{C} = \sigma_s^2 \underline{D} \underline{E} \underline{D}^H + \sigma_c^2 \underline{Q}$. The $P \times P$ ($P \leq N$) matrix $\underline{\Lambda} = \text{diag}[\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_P]$ is the diagonal matrix of eigenvalues of $\underline{C}$. It is known that the MVDR beamformer spatial filter for direction θ

with corresponding direction vector $\underline{d}(\theta)$ is

$$\underline{W}_{MV}(\theta) = \underline{R}^{-1} \underline{d}(\theta) / \underline{d}(\theta)^H \underline{R}^{-1} \underline{d}(\theta) \quad (2)$$

with power density estimate

$$P_{MV}(\theta) = 1 / \underline{d}(\theta)^H \underline{R}^{-1} \underline{d}(\theta). \quad (3)$$

The S3A power spectrum can be obtained directly from the MV spectrum of Eq. (3) by substituting Eq. (1b) into Eq. (3) and letting $\lambda_i \rightarrow \infty$ for $1 \leq i \leq P = K$ a process referred to as modal enhancement. Accordingly,

$$\lim_{\substack{\lambda_i \rightarrow \infty \\ 1 \leq i \leq K}} P_{MV}(\theta) \Big|_{\sigma_c^2=0} = 1 / (N - \sum_{i=1}^K |d(\theta)^H \underline{m}_i|^2) \quad (4)$$

$$= 1 / \sum_{i=K+1}^N |d(\theta)^H \underline{m}_i|^2$$

where $\underline{m}_i$ is the i th column of $\underline{M}$. It is emphasized that without an introduction of additional unknown parameters and a complicated prewhitening procedure the S3A technique must assume that $\sigma_c^2 = 0$ and $\underline{E} = \text{diag}[e_1, e_2, \dots, e_K]$. When either of these assumptions is incorrect degradation of the S3A spectrum results.

3.0 REDUCED DIMENSION AND RANK S3A

The major difficulty with S3A for low SNR (threshold) signals in the presence of coherent noise is that strictly on the basis of observing the eigenvalues of $\underline{R}$ it is difficult to define a signal subspace. Strictly speaking, the noise coherence matrix can be of full rank so that $P=N$ such that for $\sigma_c^2 \gg \sigma_n^2$ the "signal" directional information might not appear in the largest eigenvalues [7]. A partial solution to this problem is to specify an array preprocessing function

which reduces the S3A dimensionality, enhances the signal and suppresses the partially coherent noise in the sense of separating signal and noise dominated eigenvalues [8]. Such a function can be performed by a subarray prebeamformer defined by the $N \times M$ matrix

$$\underline{S} = \begin{bmatrix} \underline{d}_1(\theta) & \underline{0} & \dots & \underline{0} \\ \underline{0} & \underline{d}_2(\theta) & \dots & \underline{0} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \underline{0} & \underline{0} & \dots & \underline{d}_M(\theta) \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

$$= \underline{S}(\theta).$$

The vector $\underline{d}_i(\theta)$ forms the i th subarray beam from sensors $((i-1)N/M)+1$ to iN/M for $1 \leq i \leq M$ looking in direction θ . At the subarray outputs, this process serves to amplify the signals coming

from the general direction of θ and attenuate the noise level at the subarray phase centers which is due to the partially coherent noise. The coherent noise discrimination occurs if the subarray phase centers are widely spaced relative to the noise coherence distance.

As an example, consider a linear array of 24 sensors which are half-wavelength spaced at frequency ω . Let there be two signal arrivals such that

$$\underline{D}(\theta) = [\underline{d}(\theta_1) \underline{d}(\theta_2)] \quad (6)$$

with $\theta_1 = 88^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 92^\circ$. We will consider the coherent noise case where in $\sigma_c^2 = 1$ and

$$\underline{Q} = [\rho^{|i-j|}]. \quad (7)$$

The uncorrelated noise component is defined by $\sigma_n^2 = 1$. The coherence parameter in Eq. (7) is taken as $\rho = 0.5$. Using an M -subarray preprocessor reduces the dimensionality of the S3A problem from N to M . Moreover, the rank of the signal subspace can more credibly be taken as two (2) because the angular sector spanning the main lobe region of the subarray is less likely to contain more than the fundamental resolution source doublet. The coherent noise model can be envisioned as an angularly extended source centered at 90° . If the signal subspace is specified as $P=2$, the subarray S3A outperforms the full array S3A. If $P=3$ is assumed the coherent noise manifests itself as an artifact (source) at 90° . Figure 1 illustrates these effects.

4.0 COHERENT MULTIPLE ARRIVALS

It can be shown that both MVDR beamformer and S3A procedures can re-

sult in the suppression of multiple coherent arrivals [3]. If it is determined that these arrivals are signals, then signal suppression is certainly undesirable. On the otherhand, if the coherent arrivals in question are simply interference with respect to the process of detecting threshold signals, then the issue of interference suppression by such techniques as spatial averaging is certainly less important. In fact, recent treatments of interference suppression by spatial averaging would lead to a degradation in threshold signal detectability because of an effective aperture size reduction.

Figure 2 illustrates the dependence of coherent arrival suppression on the generalized cosine $\rho_1 = \frac{d(\theta_1)}{d(\theta)}$ for $\rho_2 = 0$. Figure 2(a) presents the results for $\text{SNR}_1 = 10\text{dB}$ and several values of SNR_2 . Figure 2(b) gives the results for $\text{SNR}_1 = 3\text{dB}$. The notation CC,I indicates conventional time delay-and-sum beam output power for coherent and incoherent arrivals respectively. Likewise, MVC,I indicates MVDR beam output power for coherent and incoherent arrivals. The important result demonstrated in Figure 2 is that if the arrivals are close in generalized cosine, i.e., within the main beam of a conventional beamformer, considerable suppression can occur but for high interference to noise ratio only.

5.0 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper an attempt has been made to better define the relationship between minimum variance distortionless response (MVDR) beamforming and signal subspace (wavenumber) spectrum analysis (S3A). While MVDR beamforming is generally applicable to threshold signal detection, S3A is useful only in limited angular sectors containing no more than two sources. A subarray preprocessor for S3A provides this "searchlite" capability and in addition gives partial discrimination against coherent noise. Subarray output S3A has the final advantage of vastly reduced realization complexity. As an additional result, the coherent multiple arrival problem is considered with the conclusion that, for either threshold signals or arrivals separated by greater than a beamwidth, mutual suppression should not be an issue. Moreover, the suppression of high level multiple coherent interference arrivals should not be undesirable in any event.

6.0 REFERENCES

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Figure 1(a) Full 24-sensor array eigenvalue spectrum for S3A with $SNR_1=SNR_2=-16dB$.

Figure 1(c) Four ($M=4$) subarray output eigenvalue spectrum for S3A with $SNR_1=SNR_2=-16dB$.

Figure 1(b) Reduced sector S3A corresponding to Figure 1(a).

Figure 1(d) Reduced sector S3A corresponding to Figure 1(c).

Figure 2(a) Conventional (C) and minimum variance (MV) beamformer output power for two incoherent (CI, MVI) and coherent (CC, MVC) arrivals. $SNR_1=3dB$.

Figure 2(b) Conventional and minimum variance beam output power. $SNR=10$.